

MOTIVATING TOURISM FIELD STUDENTS TO LEARN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH INTERACTIVE ACTIVITIES

Aziza Pirmatova

PhD student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Annotation: In the increasingly globalized world of tourism, proficiency in foreign languages is essential for effective communication and cultural understanding. However, motivating students in the tourism field to learn a foreign language can be challenging. This article explores the use of interactive activities as a means of enhancing motivation and language acquisition among tourism students. Drawing on research and practical examples, it examines various interactive strategies and their effectiveness in engaging students and fostering language learning.

Keywords: interactive activities, simulations, role-playing, cultural exchange programs, language immersion trips, gamification, multimedia projects.

Introduction: the tourism industry is inherently multicultural and multilingual, with interactions occurring between people from diverse linguistic backgrounds daily. As such, proficiency in foreign languages is a valuable asset for tourism professionals. However, many students in the tourism field struggle to find motivation for language learning, particularly when faced with traditional teaching methods that may lack relevance or engagement. This article explores the role of interactive activities in motivating tourism field students to learn a foreign language.

Research has shown that interactive activities can significantly enhance language learning motivation and outcomes. According to Li, interactive language learning activities stimulate students' interest and engagement, leading to greater motivation and persistence in language learning tasks. Similarly, Wang and Wen found that interactive approaches, such as role-playing and simulations, provide

opportunities for authentic language use and promote meaningful communication skills development.

Methodology: examples of interactive activities include simulations, role-playing, cultural exchange programs, language immersion trips, gamification, and multimedia projects.

Simulations and role-playing: simulating real-life scenarios allows students to practice language skills in a context that mirrors their future professional environment. Educators can design role-playing activities where students take on roles such as tour guides, travelers, or hotel staff, and engage in conversations using the target language. This not only enhances language proficiency but also develops students' confidence in their ability to communicate effectively in diverse situations.

Cultural exchange programs: organizing cultural exchange programs provides students with immersive experiences that foster language learning. Partnering with institutions or organizations in foreign countries allows students to interact with native speakers, participate in language exchanges, and gain firsthand exposure to different cultures. These experiences not only motivate students to learn the language but also deepen their understanding of cultural nuances, which is essential in the tourism industry.

Language immersion trips: integrating language learning with travel experiences can be highly motivating for tourism students. Educators can organize immersion trips to countries where the target language is spoken, combining language classes with guided tours and cultural activities. Immersion trips offer students the opportunity to practice language skills in authentic settings, interact with locals, and develop cross-cultural competence, all of which are invaluable skills in the tourism field.

Gamification: incorporating elements of gamification into language learning makes the process more engaging and interactive. Educators can use language learning apps, online games, or interactive quizzes to reinforce vocabulary, grammar, and language comprehension skills. By turning language learning into a game,

students are motivated to compete, collaborate, and achieve tangible progress, thereby enhancing their overall learning experience.

Multimedia projects: encouraging students to create multimedia projects in the target language allows them to apply their language skills in creative ways. Whether it's producing travel vlogs, designing promotional materials for tourist destinations, or writing blogs in the target language, multimedia projects provide students with authentic tasks that reflect the real-world demands of the tourism industry. This hands-on approach not only reinforces language learning but also cultivates students' creativity and digital literacy skills.

Results and discussion: interactive activities offer numerous benefits for motivating tourism field students to learn a foreign language. Simulations and role-playing, for example, provide students with opportunities for authentic language use in real-world scenarios. According to a study by García-Pastor and Marín-Aranda, simulations in tourism education allow students to practice language skills in contexts that mirror their future professional environments, thereby enhancing their language proficiency and communication competence.

Cultural exchange programs and language immersion trips offer immersive experiences that deepen students' understanding of cultural nuances and foster cross-cultural communication skills. Research by You demonstrates that participation in cultural exchange programs contributes to increased motivation and engagement among language learners, as they have the opportunity to interact with native speakers and experience the target language in authentic settings.

Gamification and multimedia projects make language learning more engaging and interactive, catering to diverse learning styles and preferences. A study by Lee and Huang highlights the effectiveness of gamified language learning platforms in enhancing students' motivation and language proficiency. By incorporating elements of competition, collaboration, and rewards, gamification stimulates students' interest and encourages active participation in language learning activities.

Similarly, multimedia projects provide students with creative outlets for applying their language skills in real-world contexts. According to a study by Park,

multimedia projects, such as creating travel vlogs or designing promotional materials in the target language, not only reinforce language learning but also develop students' digital literacy skills and cultural awareness.

Conclusion: interactive activities offer a promising avenue for motivating tourism field students to learn a foreign language. By providing opportunities for authentic language use, cultural immersion, and creative expression, interactive approaches enhance students' motivation and language acquisition outcomes. Educators in the tourism field should embrace interactive teaching methods as a means of fostering language learning motivation and preparing students for success in an increasingly globalized industry.

References:

1. García-Pastor, M. D., & Marín-Aranda, R. (2018). Simulations in tourism education: Impact on learning motivation and satisfaction. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 22, 57-65.
2. Lee, Y., & Huang, Y. (2019). The effects of gamified language learning platforms on EFL students' motivation and language proficiency. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 32(5-6), 493-512.
3. Li, M. (2019). The Role of Interactive Language Learning Activities in Improving Students' Motivation. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(5), 963-969.
4. Wang, Y., & Wen, X. (2020). Interactive Teaching Methods in Foreign Language Education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(1), 171-182.
5. You, J. (2017). The impact of cultural exchange programs on motivation in foreign language learning. *Language Teaching Research*, 21(5), 643-663.